

The PGI gene had three alleles: Pgi³⁵, Pgi¹⁰⁰, and Pgi¹⁰⁵ designated as 1, 2, and 3, respectively. The IDH gene had two alleles: Idh⁹³ and Idh¹⁰⁰, designated as 1 and 2. The MDH gene had two alleles: Mdh¹⁰⁰ and Mdh¹⁰⁹, designated as 2 and 3.

The allele frequencies and the heterozygosities of the two populations are in Table 2. Biotype 1 had a slightly higher mean heterozygosity ($\bar{H}$) (0.068) than biotype 3 (0.023), mainly because of a higher number of heterozygotes at locus PCI.

As far as those three loci are concerned, biotype 1 exhibits more genetic variation than biotype 3. A more conclusive statement regarding the extent of variation could be obtained by increasing the number of protein loci investigated. □

Effect of temperature on brown planthopper (BPH) feeding

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We studied the effect of temperature on BPH feeding. BPH were collected from the stubble in rice fields on 5 Oct, after the crop was harvested and when mean temperature fell below 16 to 13°C.

Two 4th-instar nymphs and 2 adult BPH were placed in a mylar film cage and allowed to feed on 15-d-old plants of susceptible Milyang 23 for 24 h at a constant temperature. Area (mm²) of the honeydew spots excreted by BPH on Toyo No. 2 filter paper dipped in a solution of bromocresol green (2 mg/ml ethanol) was measured.

BPH feeding significantly decreased at lower temperatures (see table). At 9°C there was no feeding activity at nymph or adult stages. □

Area of honeydew spots excreted by BPH at different temperatures, Suweon, Korea.

Temp (°C)	Area (mm ²) ^a in 24 h		
	Nymphs	Adults	Mean
26	30.1 a	22.9 a	26.5
20	7.8 b	19.5 a	13.7
16	3.2 bc	3.5 b	3.4
13	5.4 bc	4.4 b	4.9
9	0.0 c	0.0 b	0.0

^a Mean for 2 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Pest management and control WEEDS

Weed control in dry-seeded lowland rice With bentazon and bentazon combined with 2,4-D

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Dry-seeded lowland rainfed rice has good potential in northeastern India, but heavy weed infestation is a serious constraint. In 1983, we evaluated bentazon and bentazon + 2,4-D for weed control.

In northeastern India, the typical dry-seeded field weed flora is 68-75% sedges, 15-20% broadleaf weeds, and 5-10% grasses. Bentazon was applied by a knapsack sprayer at 1.5 and 2.0 kg/ha alone or in combination with the amine salt of 2,4-D at 1.0 kg/ha with 1,000 litres of water/ha as a directed spray 15 d after rice germination.

Bentazon alone and bentazon + 2,4-D did not have a phytotoxic effect on rice seedlings. Bentazon + 2,4-D significantly

reduced weed population and weed dry matter accumulation compared with bentazon alone and grain yield was similar to that with conventional hand weeding (see table). With unchecked weed competition, grain yield was reduced 33.3%. □

Effect of different bentazon concentrations and bentazon combined with 2,4-D on rice grain yield and weed mortality, Bhubaneswar, India.^a

Treatment	Weeds (no./m ²) at 25 DAS	Weed dry wt (g/m ²) at 90 DAS	Grain yield t/ha
Bentazon @ 1.5 kg/ha	101.2	87	3.3 c
Bentazon @ 2.0 kg/ha	79.6	69	3.6 b
Bentazon @ 1.5 kg/ha + 2,4-D @ 1.0 kg/ha	59.4	57	3.9 a
Bentazon @ 2.0 kg/ha + 2,4-D @ 1.0 kg/ha	47.8	53	4.0 a
Conventional hand weeding (25 and 45 DAS)	398.6	28	4.2 a
Unweeded control	415.2	210	2.8 d
CD at 5%	19.4	10.4	0.27

^a DAS = days after seeding.

Effect of rice crop residue management on weed growth in lowland rice

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At TNAU, Coimbatore, in 1981 summer and monsoon seasons, we found that incorporating rice crop residues reduced weed dry matter production (DMP). Treatments were in a randomized split-plot design with three replications.

In summer, treatments were control, no residue incorporated (S₀); 10 t rice

Effect of rice crop residue management on weed growth in lowland rice. TNAU, Coimbatore, India.

Treatment		Summer					Monsoon				
		Plant ht (cm)	LAI	BGA (kg/10 m ²) fresh wt	DMP of weeds (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Plant ht (cm)	LAI	BGA (kg/10 m ²) fresh wt	DMP of weeds (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
S ₀ B ₀	N ₅₀	61	3.66	0.19	343	4.6	56	2.44	0.12	435	3.5
	N ₇₅	72	4.37	0.48	271	4.8	67	3.75	0.36	381	3.6
	N ₁₀₀	78	5.18	0.44	261	5.0	70	3.82	0.34	404	3.8
S ₀ B ₁	N ₅₀	70	3.81	0.32	307	4.7	75	2.62	0.39	521	3.7
	N ₇₅	84	4.68	0.58	269	5.0	77	3.79	0.70	446	3.9
	N ₁₀₀	85	5.44	0.54	272	5.2	80	3.92	0.66	427	4.1
S ₁ B ₀	N ₅₀	73	5.39	0.70	23	5.5	75	4.81	0.86	25	4.5
	N ₇₅	81	6.97	1.43	20	5.8	79	5.38	1.63	18	4.8
	N ₁₀₀	87	6.87	0.93	15	5.7	80	5.40	1.16	19	4.8
S ₁ B ₁	N ₅₀	75	5.65	2.92	38	6.0	76	4.87	3.13	37	5.0
	N ₇₅	80	7.17	4.58	18	6.5	79	5.54	5.28	14	5.5
	N ₁₀₀	84	6.90	3.97	17	6.3	85	5.66	5.02	15	5.5
S ₂ B ₀	N ₅₀	73	5.37	0.73	52	4.8	75	4.40	1.03	41	4.0
	N ₇₅	79	6.74	1.15	37	5.4	79	5.20	1.39	24	4.4
	N ₁₀₀	84	6.42	0.96	43	5.2	81	5.27	1.10	29	4.4
S ₂ B ₁	N ₅₀	72	5.44	1.82	62	5.3	74	4.27	2.07	42	4.5
	N ₇₅	83	6.83	2.81	44	5.9	80	5.31	3.84	36	5.0
	N ₁₀₀	85	6.67	2.64	51	5.6	83	5.47	3.90	33	4.9
S ₃ B ₀	N ₅₀	77	5.69	0.77	31	4.9	74	4.11	1.08	30	4.2
	N ₇₅	80	6.80	1.31	22	5.6	80	5.32	1.83	24	4.8
	N ₁₀₀	90	6.71	0.97	27	5.5	84	5.43	1.67	20	4.8
S ₃ B ₁	N ₅₀	15	5.78	3.23	35	5.6	75	4.73	4.19	32	4.8
	N ₇₅	80	6.99	4.72	25	6.1	79	5.49	6.30	22	5.2
	N ₁₀₀	88	6.82	4.67	24	5.9	85	5.52	6.02	19	5.2
CD (0.05)											
Residues (s)		3.9	0.09	0.20	14.4	79	1.9	0.07	0.34	8.4	62
Bonemeal (B)		ns	0.07	0.14	ns	55	1.4	0.05	0.24	6.0	44
S × B		5.6	0.13	0.28	ns	111	2.8	0.10	0.47	11.0	87
N levels		2.3	0.10	ns	9.4	56	2.0	0.07	0.17	4.9	61
S at N		ns	0.19	ns	21.1	12	ns	0.13	0.43	11.2	93
N at S		ns	0.21	ns	18.8	112	ns	0.14	0.34	9.8	122
B at N		ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.31	7.9	ns
N at B		ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.24	6.9	ns

long straw/ha (S₁); 4.6 t 30-cm rice stubble/ha (S₂); and 10 t composted rice straw/ha (S₃), incorporated with 50 (N₅₀), 75 (N₇₅), or 100 (N₁₀₀) kg N/ha, with 22 kg P/ha as bonemeal (B₁) and without bonemeal (B₀).

The following monsoon crop was grown in the same field with N₅₀, N₇₅, or N₁₀₀ and B₁ (11 kg P/ha as bonemeal) and B₀ to study the residual effect of residue incorporation.

A bulk crop of IR20 was raised in the experimental field during the northeast monsoon. Plots where 30 cm IR20 stubble were incorporated were pegged. In other plots, stubble was removed at the base and the field was puddled and leveled, except in S₂. In S₂, stubble was incorporated using a spade. Rice crop residue was incorporated 2 wk before planting in 4 × 5-m² plots (net 3.3 × 4.8 m²).

Seedling age at transplanting was 22 d in summer and 24 d in monsoon. Spacing was 15 × 20 cm². The summer crop of Co 37 (IET849) was transplanted 25 Mar and harvested 22 Jun. The monsoon crop was planted 31 Jul and harvested 4 Nov. In monsoon, all residue was incorporated by spade.

Five plants per plot were randomly tagged. At flowering, plant height; leaf area index (LAI), by length and width method; and blue-green algae (BGA) fresh weight, using a 50 × 50-cm² quadrat and expressed in kg/m², were recorded. Grain yield at 14% moisture was expressed as kg/ha. Weed DMP was estimated by taking samples from a 50 × 50-cm² quadrat in each plot, and was expressed in kg/ha.

Incorporation of rice crop residues significantly reduced weed DMP in both

seasons and significantly increased grain yield. In both seasons, S₁ and S₃ had similar results and lowest weed DMP (see table). Weed population was less with rice residue incorporation because of increased rice plant height, LAI, and BGA growth. Increasing N levels decreased weed DMP. N₇₅ was similar to N₁₀₀ in both seasons for all treatments.

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